

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

The production of irregularity in Europe

How to improve the living and labour
conditions of irregularised migrant
workers and their households

Policy Brief

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Summary

Migrants' irregular status in Europe is commonly framed as a border control issue, unauthorised entry or failed return. However, irregularity and legal precarity are structurally produced through the interaction of migration, labour, welfare and family policy regimes at the EU and national levels.

Legal precarity often occurs due to restrictive residence permit renewal criteria, employer dependency, income thresholds, administrative delays and limited status transitions. These are embedded in segmented labour markets and shaped by racialised and gendered hierarchies, meaning that precarity becomes economically functional and politically normalised.

Comparative research in Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, the UK and at the EU level shows that irregularity is a structural feature of contemporary labour regimes. In agriculture, platform-based delivery and domestic and care work, fragmented contracts, subcontracting chains and employer-tied permits convert migration control into labour discipline, exposing migrant workers to exploitation and constrained mobility. Legal precarity is unevenly distributed, disproportionately affecting racialised groups and reshaping family life, caregiving arrangements and intergenerational stability.

Political and media narratives exacerbate these dynamics by reducing irregularity to narratives based around crisis and criminality, obscuring the administrative and labour market mechanisms driving it. Public perception frequently overestimates irregular migrant populations and reproduces hierarchies of deservingness, legitimising deterrence-focused governance and overlooking irregular migrant workers' realities.

This Policy Brief calls for reducing the structural drivers of irregularisation in residence and migration regimes, mainstreaming fundamental and socio-economic rights and non-discrimination in migration governance, separating labour protection from immigration control and addressing housing conditions as a structural dimension of labour precarity and irregularisation.

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Introduction

Migrants' irregular status in Europe is commonly framed as a border control, unauthorised entry or failed return issue. Yet evidence from the Horizon Europe-UK Research and Innovation [I-CLAIM](#) project shows that irregularity and legal precarity are produced through the ordinary functioning of migration, labour, welfare and family policy regimes at the EU and national levels.

Irregularity is not a fixed legal category. It should be understood as a process of irregularisation. In six European countries and at the EU level, I-CLAIM research demonstrates that irregularity and legal precarity are structurally embedded in labour regimes. They disproportionately affect racialised groups, have heavily gendered impacts, reshape family life and caregiving arrangements, and are sustained by political and media narratives linking irregular migration to crisis, criminality and control.

Addressing irregularity and legal precarity requires rethinking of the dynamics between migration governance, labour regulation and fundamental rights obligations, rather than exclusively focusing on improving return rates or strengthening external borders.

This Policy Brief presents four overarching policy recommendations for improving the living and working conditions of irregularised migrant workers in Europe:

- i. reducing the structural drivers of irregularisation in residence and migration regimes;
- ii. mainstreaming fundamental rights, socio-economic rights and non-discrimination across irregular migration governance;
- iii. separating labour protection from migration control and upholding labour rights for all workers, irrespective of their migration status or (un)declared nature of their work;
- iv. addressing housing conditions as a structural dimension of labour precarity and irregularisation.

Methodology

This Policy Brief synthesises findings from the [I-CLAIM](#) Horizon Europe-UKRI project. It draws from comparative research conducted in [Finland](#), [Germany](#), [Italy](#), [the Netherlands](#), [Poland](#), [the UK](#) (referred collectively as 'I-CLAIM countries' from here onwards) and at the [EU](#) level.

The findings build on national ethnographic fieldwork, interviews, EU-level analysis and consultations with national and EU stakeholders, including policymakers, civil society organisations, social partners and practitioners. These exchanges informed the policy recommendations presented below.

Main research findings

MAIN FINDING #1:

Irregularity and legal precarity are produced by regulatory frameworks governing residence, work, welfare and family life at the national and EU levels – they are not only a border or return issue.

Irregularity and legal precarity do not result from a single unlawful entry, failed regularisation procedure or impossible return. They are produced through intersecting legal frameworks, administrative practices and labour market regimes operating at the national and EU levels. The infrastructures of irregularity are created across migration law, asylum systems, labour regulation, welfare access and family reunification rules.

At the national level, irregularity and legal precarity often emerge through ordinary regulatory mechanisms. Residence permits are tied to continuous employment, income thresholds, housing requirements or employer sponsorship. The loss of a job, a relationship breakdown, a bureaucratic delay or a failure to meet renewal conditions can trigger irregularity. Restrictive family reunification rules, limited access to humanitarian permits and high administrative fees narrow down pathways to status stabilisation.

In Germany, the *Duldung* system suspends deportation without granting residence, creating prolonged legal limbo ([Rheindorf et al., 2024](#)). In the Netherlands, the *Koppelingswet* links access to social services to lawful residence, embedding immigration control within welfare governance ([Hajer et al., 2024](#)). In Italy and Finland, successive reforms restricting humanitarian or special protection permits have pushed people into irregular situations when returns are impossible ([Palumbo & Marchetti, 2024](#); [Merikoski et al., 2024](#)). In the UK, ‘hostile environment’ policies have delegated migration control to landlords, employers and service providers, diffusing immigration enforcement across everyday life ([Piemontese & Sigona, 2024](#)). These national frameworks demonstrate that irregularity is produced through internal regulatory choices regarding work, welfare and family life.

At the EU level, irregularity is embedded in the historical development of Schengen and Dublin cooperation ([Carrera & Colombi, 2025](#)). Abolishing internal border controls was accompanied by ‘compensatory’ security measures prioritising visa control, surveillance and the policing of third-country nationals. Over the years, with the increasing centralisation of power and in response to specific political priorities, the European Commission has primarily adopted a home affairs and criminalisation approach centred on border control, deterrence and return ([Carrera & Colombi, 2025](#)).

Legislative initiatives falling under the [Pact on Migration and Asylum](#) or the [proposed Return Regulation](#) focus on accelerating procedures, expanding safe third country concepts and increasing return rates, often without assessing the impacts on fundamental rights. Enforcing existing socio-economic rights instruments and protective elements – such as access to residence permits under Article 6 of the [Return Directive](#) – is but a secondary consideration. DG HOME’s migration control framing has frequently overshadowed employment, non-discrimination and social inclusion approaches located in DG EMPL and DG JUST. Consequently, irregularised individuals are primarily considered as individuals to expel rather than workers or rights-holders.

The boundary between regularity and irregularity is fluid and policy-driven. Many irregularised individuals entered through regular channels and only become irregular due to restrictive renewal criteria, procedural

bottlenecks or the absence of viable regularisation mechanisms. The ‘irregular condition’ experienced by migrants is the consequence of these governance choices – chronic insecurity, constrained mobility, dependence on informal arrangements and heightened vulnerability to exploitation. These effects vary but they are structurally linked to regulatory design.

Irregularity should therefore be understood as an ‘assemblage’: a constellation of EU and national laws, bureaucratic practices, labour market structures and political narratives that actively come together to produce legal insecurity.

MAIN FINDING #2:**Irregularity and legal precarity are not anomalies but structural features of contemporary labour regimes, exposing irregularised migrant workers to different forms of exploitation, precarity and vulnerability**

I-CLAIM's comparative findings ([van Liempt et al., 2026](#)) on labour sectors highlight that labour regimes in agriculture, delivery and logistics, and domestic and care work rely on fragmented contracts, subcontracting chains, seasonal recruitment, the ‘platform economy’ and limited enforcement. This creates conditions where legal insecurity becomes economically functional. Migration and labour governance intersect to produce a workforce that is flexible, disposable and dependent, particularly when residence permits are tied to specific employers, sectors or short-term contracts.

Irregularised and precarious migrant workers are concentrated in roles characterised by long working hours, income instability, piece-rate payment, unsafe conditions and limited access to social protection. In the agricultural sector, seasonal and temporary schemes, combined with opaque recruitment practices and housing dependency, cause workers to fall into debt exposure and limit their bargaining power. In platform-based delivery work, workers must navigate algorithmic management, unpredictable earnings and risks of deactivation, alongside intensified policing and identity checks. In domestic and care work, work takes place mostly in private homes, where informal arrangements are prevalent and effective inspection is largely absent. This creates environments where underpayment, excessive hours and abuse can persist with minimal oversight.

Legal precarity amplifies labour vulnerabilities. Employer-tied permits, short renewal cycles, income thresholds and limited mobility across sectors restrict workers' ability to change jobs or refuse abusive conditions without risking a loss of status. This produces what participants describe as conditions of ‘unfreedom’ or ‘slavery’, where formal legality coexists with constrained agency. Even when workers hold regular permits, conditions for residence renewal and family rights aggravate their dependence and discourages complaints. Irregularised workers often remain in informal or undeclared employment with little access to redress, while firewalls between labour enforcement and immigration control remain weak or absent.

Housing conditions are a central dimension of labour precarity and irregularisation. Migrant workers in agriculture, domestic and care work, and platform-based delivery frequently rely on employers, labour intermediaries or informal networks for accommodation. This can exacerbate their dependency and limit their ability to change employment or report abusive practices. Ethnic segregation and spatial marginalisation concentrate racialised groups in lower-quality housing and limit access to employment, services and social mobility (see [ENAR, 2024](#); [FRA, 2017](#)).

At the same time, housing requirements embedded in migration governance frameworks – including proof of suitable accommodation for residence permits or family reunification – often clash with discrimination in the rental market, high housing costs and unstable employment. In practice, these factors can make it difficult for migrant workers to secure independent accommodation, expose them to inadequate housing conditions, wage deductions and the risk of homelessness when their employment ends, thus contributing to legal precarity and irregularisation.

These dynamics show that irregularity is embedded within the political economy of labour markets. Sectors facing labour shortages systematically depend on migrants while maintaining legal and contractual arrangements that sustain flexibility and reduce costs. Subcontracting chains, labour intermediaries and platform-based management structures further aggravate workers' dependence and blur accountability for labour standards. The result is a stratified labour regime where legal insecurity and exploitability are unevenly distributed but structurally produced. Irregularity operates as a governance tool that converts migration control into labour discipline, exposing migrant workers to various forms of exploitation and vulnerability across Europe.

MAIN FINDING #3:**Irregularity and legal precarity are racialised in their production and effects, disproportionately affecting individuals based on race, ethnicity and national origin**

Irregularity is not neutral or purely administrative. I-CLAIM research on irregular migration's racial logic ([Piemontese et al., 2026](#)) shows that migration governance operates through stratified hierarchies of mobility and belonging that varies depending on nationalities, regions of origin and racialised groups. Access to visas, labour permits, status renewal and family reunification is unevenly structured, while enforcement practices and vulnerability recognition are shaped by implicit and explicit racialised assumptions.

Racialised young men – particularly from African and Middle Eastern backgrounds – are disproportionately framed as security threats, economic opportunists or culturally incompatible. This legitimises intensified border control, policing, identity checks and administrative scrutiny. At the same time, their exposure to labour exploitation and unsafe working conditions remains under-recognised. By contrast, some national groups are considered desirable, particularly in shortage sectors, yet they remain confined to short-term, employer-dependent or sector-specific permits that institutionalise legal fragility rather than providing pathways to long-term stability.

Racialisation happens not only through discourse but also through administrative practice. Decisions on residence renewal, integration assessments and access to protection often rely on subjective stability evaluations and deservingness, embedding hierarchies of moral worth within governance. Certain groups are more likely to face greater obstacles to regularisation, disproportionate housing discrimination and racial profiling in public space and labour inspections. Vulnerability is also unevenly acknowledged: women and children may be recognised within humanitarian frames, while racialised men's structural exposure to exploitation, violence and precarity remains masked by security narratives.

Consequently, irregularity functions as a mechanism of racial stratification. Legal precarity intersects with labour market segmentation and public discourse, unevenly distributing insecurity across groups, shaping

access to rights, protection, mobility and long-term settlement. Irregularity is not simply a legal status but a governance outcome that reproduces racialised hierarchies within European migration regimes.

MAIN FINDING #4:**Irregularity and legal precarity have deep gendered and household effects that reshape family life, caregiving arrangements and intergenerational stability.**

Irregularity and legal precarity do not affect individuals in a vacuum. They restructure households, redistribute care responsibilities and generate intergenerational consequences. I-CLAIM research ([Näre et al., 2026](#)) shows that residence insecurity, employer dependency, income thresholds and fragmented labour markets directly shape family formation, reunification and children's wellbeing.

Regular status is increasingly conditional on continuous employment, appropriate income and housing, favouring stable breadwinner models and marginalising households dependent on low-paid, seasonal or care-related work. These requirements disproportionately disadvantage women, who are overrepresented in the undervalued domestic and care sectors and more likely to experience employment interruptions due to caregiving. Meanwhile, men in precarious sectors, such as agriculture and delivery, struggle with unstable income and contracts, undermining their ability to meet renewal and reunification criteria. Gender-segmented labour markets and pay gaps directly affect access to residence security.

Precarious working conditions – long hours, unpredictable schedules, piece-rate payment and temporary permits – limit the capacity to sustain relationships, provide care or plan for the future. Workers report delaying reunification, living in overcrowded or informal housing or maintaining prolonged transnational family arrangements due to being unable to meet administrative thresholds. Pregnancy-based protections and humanitarian safeguards are often temporary and non-convertible, producing legal limbo for both parents and children alike. For households with children, residence uncertainty and parental exhaustion affect access to education, healthcare and stable social environments, while enforcement-oriented measures extend insecurity into welfare and public services.

Women frequently carry a dual burden of paid and unpaid reproductive labour, combining intensive work with transnational caregiving or single parenthood under legal insecurity. At the same time, men in platform-based or seasonal sectors describe intense pressure to work continuously to meet remittance and family obligations, often postponing relationships or long-term settlement. These dynamics reveal that irregularity also operates within households, shaping caregiving arrangements, delaying family stability and transmitting insecurity across generations.

MAIN FINDING #5:**Media and political narratives contribute to irregularity and shape public perceptions**

Migration remains a central issue in European public debate. Across the six I-CLAIM countries and at the EU level, discourse analysis shows that irregularity is predominantly constructed through securitised, economic and moral frames ([Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025](#)). Media and political narratives reduce irregularity to border crossings, asylum rejection and criminality, while largely omitting the administrative and labour market mechanisms that produce irregularisation.

Irregularised migrants are often presented as economic units – a labour force to address demographic decline or as burdens on welfare systems – and as security threats linked to border control and sovereignty. Only civil society actors consistently portray them as rights-holders embedded in families, workplaces and communities. While national patterns differ – with securitisation particularly dominant in Poland and the UK, and labour market and humanitarian framings more visible in Italy and Germany – crisis narratives remain pervasive and reinforce restrictive policy responses. Political actors deploy migration strategically, with right-wing parties emphasising deterrence and sovereignty, while left-leaning actors focus more on governance, integration and labour contributions.

The discourse is also deeply racialised and gendered. Young racialised men are frequently depicted as security risks, while women and children are framed as vulnerable and more deserving of protection. This legitimises different levels of access to rights and protection.

Public perceptions broadly reproduce these constructions ([Lessard-Phillips & Sigona, 2025](#); [Lessard-Phillips et al., 2025a](#); [Lessard-Phillips et al., 2025b](#); [Lessard-Phillips et al. 2026a](#); [Lessard-Phillips et al. 2026b](#); [Lessard-Phillips et al. 2026c](#)). Survey evidence shows that irregular migrant populations are systematically overestimated and that irregularity is often associated with border crossings, rather than administrative pathways such as visa overstays. Attitudes are shaped by proximity, gender and race, with conditions of deservingness tied to family life, vulnerability and perceived integration. While concerns about irregular migration are widespread, there is comparatively stronger support for regularisation and children's rights than for increased welfare access.

Policy recommendations

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #1:

Reduce the structural drivers of irregularisation in residence and migration regimes

Irregularity is often produced by institutional design, not by individual behaviour. Short-term permits, employer dependency, rigid income thresholds, restrictive renewal criteria and limited pathways between residence categories create structural conditions where migrants lose lawful status despite ongoing social and economic participation.

At the EU level, the Commission should assess how existing EU migration instruments and implementation practices contribute to status insecurity and irregularisation. Attention should be given to how residence renewal requirements interact with labour market realities in sectors characterised by seasonal work, subcontracting chains and fluctuating income. With this in mind, the Commission should examine how existing labour migration directives currently function – including the [Single Permit Directive](#) and the [Seasonal Workers Directive](#) – to ensure that they do not inadvertently aggravate employer dependency or produce avoidable loss of status.

The EU's migration policy should also clarify and streamline transitions between residence categories – including student, seasonal, humanitarian and temporary protection statuses – for individuals who are already present and economically or socially embedded in a Member State. Existing legal possibilities under EU law should be better used to grant residence permits, including permits on compassionate, humanitarian or other reasons contained in Article 6(4) of the [Return Directive](#), particularly in situations where return is not feasible and individuals have developed ties within European societies.

Regarding the ongoing negotiations over the proposed [Return Regulation](#), the European Commission and co-legislators should ensure that migration policy does not rely exclusively on expanding coercive enforcement tools – including detention, intensified detection practices, policing operations and obligations to cooperate – but instead addresses the structural drivers that generate irregularisation, including restrictive residence regimes, limited status transitions and the absence of regularisation pathways.

At the national level, the Member States and the UK should review residence renewal criteria, income thresholds, housing requirements and administrative procedures that results in a loss of status. Administrative delays, short employment interruptions or temporary changes in family circumstances should not automatically lead to irregularisation.

National governments should also introduce clearer and more accessible mechanisms for transitioning to another status or regularisation where migrants have created ties through work, family life or long-term residence. Transparent and predictable pathways to residence stability can reduce exploitation, improve labour market transparency and contribute towards limiting the structural production of irregularity.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #2:

Fundamental rights, socio-economic rights and non-discrimination across migration governance should be mainstreamed

Addressing irregularity and legal precarity means aligning migration governance with existing national, EU and international obligations on human rights, equality and social rights. Migration policy should not operate as a silo centred exclusively on border control and return, but as a field of governance subject to the same constitutional and social standards as other areas of EU and national law.

At the EU level, the Commission should ensure that legislative initiatives on migration are systematically assessed for their impact on fundamental rights, equality and non-discrimination, in line with the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the [EU Better Regulation](#) framework. Fundamental rights considerations should be embedded from the earliest stages of policy design.

The Commission should also better monitor Member States' compliance with EU law where administrative practices restrict access to essential services, undermine access to remedies or generate discriminatory outcomes in residency, welfare or labour contexts. Attention should be given to the effective implementation of existing EU instruments that provide safeguards for individuals in legal precarity, including the [Victims' Rights Directive](#), the [Anti-Trafficking Directive](#) and relevant EU equality legislation.

Migration policy should also be more explicitly integrated when implementing EU equality frameworks, including the EU [Anti-Racism Strategy](#), the [Gender Equality Strategy](#) and the EU [Strategy on the Rights of the Child](#). Migration-related vulnerabilities and discriminatory impacts should be systematically considered within these strategies, recognising that residence regimes, migration enforcement practices and access to welfare systems may produce disproportionate effects across gender, nationality and racialised groups.

At the national level, the Member States and the UK should review residence, welfare and administrative frameworks to ensure that access to essential services, complaint mechanisms and judicial remedies is not indirectly conditional on cooperating with immigration enforcement. Racial profiling and discriminatory

policing practices should be addressed through clear legal safeguards, oversight mechanisms and training for administrative and law enforcement authorities.

Migration policy should ultimately reflect the commitments to human dignity, equality and social rights contained in EU law and national constitutions, ensuring that irregularised persons are recognised as rights-holders and that protection against labour exploitation, violence and discrimination does not depend on restrictive notions of vulnerability or deservingness.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #3:**Separate labour protection from migration control and uphold workers' rights for all workers, irrespective of migration status or the (un)declared nature of work**

Legal insecurity and irregularity is sustained by economic incentives and a segmented labour market. Effective reforms require separating labour protection from immigration control and ensuring that workers' rights are not contingent on residence status.

At the EU level, the Commission should implement and enforce existing labour laws in a way that protects irregularised and undocumented workers. Attention should be given to the protective provisions of the [Employers' Sanctions Directive](#), including access to back pay, compensation and complaint mechanisms. The [Seasonal Workers Directive](#) and the [Platform Work Directive](#) should also be implemented in sectors where migrant workers frequently operate through subcontracting chains, labour intermediaries or digital platform arrangements.

These efforts should be framed within the broader commitments of the [European Pillar of Social Rights](#), which affirms the right to fair working conditions, equal opportunities and access to social protection for all workers. Implementing EU and national labour standards should also be consistent with the [European Social Charter](#) and relevant [International Labour Organisation](#) conventions on labour inspection, decent work, forced labour and the protection of migrant workers.

Operational firewalls between labour inspectorates and immigration authorities should be promoted as a matter of labour market integrity, enabling workers to report exploitation, unsafe conditions or harassment without fear of detection or removal. Cooperating through the [European Labour Authority](#) should explicitly address sectors marked by undeclared or irregularised work. Joint inspections, information campaigns and cooperation with trade unions, social partners and civil society organisations can play a significant role in ensuring that migrant workers receive accessible information on labour rights and available remedies irrespective of their residence status.

At the national level, being dependent on employers for residency should be reduced by facilitating mobility across employers, contracts and sectors and by allowing status transitions for workers who are already present and engaged in employment. Temporary unemployment, illness or income fluctuation should not automatically result in a loss of residence status, particularly when individuals remain integrated in labour markets or family structures.

Labour inspectorates should be adequately resourced and empowered to monitor sectors marked by informality, spatial isolation or fragmented subcontracting chains. Wherever serious violations such as labour exploitation, trafficking or severe abuse are identified, Member States should ensure that third-

country nationals can obtain secure residence permits and access to protection under national law and relevant EU instruments, including the [Anti-Trafficking Directive](#) and the [Victims' Rights Directive](#).

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #4:**Address housing conditions as a structural dimension of labour precarity and irregularisation**

Housing conditions constitute a central dimension of migrant workers' living and working environments and play a significant role in shaping the dynamics of labour exploitation, undeclared work and irregularisation. In sectors such as agriculture, domestic and care work; and the platform economy, migrant workers frequently depend on employers, labour intermediaries or informal networks to access accommodation. This dependency can reinforce unequal power dynamics in the workplace, restrict workers' mobility between employers and increase vulnerability to exploitative practices.

At the EU level, the Commission should more strongly monitor and enforce existing EU legislation regarding accommodation conditions for migrant workers. Attention should be given to provisions contained in sectoral migration instruments, including the [Seasonal Workers Directive](#), which requires Member States to ensure that accommodation provided to migrant workers meets adequate standards of safety and dignity.

EU initiatives should explicitly address the gendered and racialised patterns of labour segmentation in migrant-reliant sectors, to mitigate housing-related vulnerabilities affecting workers in feminised sectors as well as racialised migrant groups facing discrimination in housing markets. These issues should be adequately reflected in EU-wide policy coordination, monitoring and enforcement activities, including in broader EU housing and social policy initiatives such as the [European Affordable Housing Plan](#), the [New European Bauhaus](#) and the [European Pillar of Social Rights](#).

At the national level, accommodation arrangements linked to employment must not become mechanisms of dependency or labour control. Where housing is provided by employers or intermediaries, it should comply with minimum standards of safety, sanitation, privacy and non-discrimination, and remain subject to effective oversight by competent authorities.

National governments should also address structural barriers that migrant workers face in accessing independent housing in local rental markets. Housing requirements attached to residence permits should be reviewed to ensure that they do not constitute disproportionate barriers contributing to a loss of legal status. Attention should be paid to the specific housing conditions for women working in domestic and care sectors, as well as racialised migrant workers who may face intersecting forms of labour exploitation and housing discrimination.

I-CLAIM Comparative Reports and Policy Briefs.

Comparative reports

- **THE LEGAL AND POLICY INFRASTRUCTURE OF MIGRANT IRREGULARITY:** Näre, L., Palumbo, L., Merikoski, P., & Marchetti, S. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Migrant Irregularity. Comparative Report.* I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/12564073>
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